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Quantum device prototype

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Introduction

The production phase of the field version of the quantum gravimeter (AQG-B) under WP2 has involved (i) the integration of the different components, (ii) the optimization of the sequence parameters and (iii) the characterization of the device prior to shipment. Delays occurred before the production phase due to late delivery of some critical components, such as the pyramid used to trap the atoms. Because of these delays, the integration of the prototype ended in January 2020, instead of October 2019. Despite this shift in the schedule, we managed to have the device running in a laboratory environment in March 2020 and providing measurements of g at the required level of sensitivity. Under normal conditions, Muquans would have followed the plan agreed with the partners during the “pre-deployment” meeting (February 2020), involving the shipment of the prototype of AQG-B to Catania in July 2020. However, the confinement measures put in place by the French government to fight the spread of the COVID-19 could lead to delays with respect to the expected schedule.

This document consists in a report rather than the delivery of a demonstrator for the reasons listed above. However, we strongly emphasize that the instrument is functional, provides gravity measurements, and is currently under test and characterization. This report presents the advancements in the production of the AQG-B prototype and the planning until the installation on Mt. Etna.

The first section provides general information on the prototype.

Section 2 describes the current status of the prototype.

Section 3 shows the results obtained with the prototype so far.

Finally, section 4 presents the next steps and schedule, including both the initial program, and a risk analysis with possible delay scenarios due to the COVID-19 pandemic.

1. General information

The AQG-B has the same overall architecture and specifications as the laboratory version of the quantum gravimeter (AQG-A, see Ref. 1), but its system has been completely redesigned to be compatible to outdoor operation. In particular, this version operates over an extended external temperature range with a relatively low power consumption, and with the possibility to use batteries as a power source. The weight of each module has been kept as low as possible (below 40 kg, see Table 3) to make transportation and manipulations as convenient as possible. Furthermore, the number of connectors has been reduced, and they have been optimized for an easy installation and to avoid possible misconnections. Finally, the sensor head can be moved within a 15 meters radius without powering off the device (5 meters in the initial version).

1.1 Targeted specifications

Performance	Description
Sensitivity	50 $\mu\text{Gal}/\sqrt{t}$ at quiet site 75 $\mu\text{Gal}/\sqrt{t}$ at Muquans' premises (city center)
Long term stability	$\sim 1 \mu\text{Gal}$
Repeatability	$\sim 2 \mu\text{Gal}$
Accuracy	$< 15 \mu\text{Gal}$

Table 1- Targeted performance of the AQG-B.

1.2 Size and weight

Element + transportation case	Weight (kg)	Length x Height x Depth (cm)
Power supply	30	62 x 40 x 90
Laser	40	62 x 50 x 88
Air-conditioner	25	62 x 50 x 35
Sensor head	55	55 x 55 x 106
Cables and accessories	54	55 x 55 x 106

Table 2- Size and weight of each element in its transportation case.

To help the reader to assess the work that has been done, we include some pictures of a pre-prototype of field AQG that was developed in the context of NEWTON-g, in parallel with the gravimeter that will be shipped to Catania, in order to make tests and validate technical choices.

Figure 1- Pictures of the different elements of a pre-prototype, in their transportation cases. From top left to bottom right: power supply module, laser system, air conditioner, sensor head and cables and accessories case.

Element in operation	Weight (kg)	Length x Height x Depth (cm)
Power supply module (1)	30	62 x 40 x 90
Air-conditioner (2) case fastened on the laser module (3)	57	62 x 50 x 108
	Weight (kg)	Height x Diameter (cm)
Sensor head (4)	35	84 x 38

Table 3- Size and weight of each element in operation.

Figure 2- Pictures of assembled modules from a pre-prototype: An AQG-B in operation configuration. The numbers refer to the modules in the Table 3.

1.3 Technical ratings

Name	Description
Supply voltage	230 V AC or 24 V DC on battery
Power	Continuous operation: 500 W max Powering on phase: power surge up to 1.5 kW (ms or s timescale)

Table 4- Electrical ratings.

Name	Description
Laser Class/Regime	3B/CW
Output power	300 mW max
Wavelength	780 nm

Table 5- Optical ratings.

2. Current status of the AQQ-B

2.1 Procurements

Table 6 summarizes the current status of supplying for the key elements of the AQQ-B. The expected delivery dates of the items not yet received is uncertain because of the implications of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Elements	Available (yes/no)	Reception date if available	Expected delivery date if not available
Operational laser system	yes	13/01/2020	
Definitive laser system case	yes	10/02/2020	
Operational air conditioner	yes	13/01/2020	
Definitive power supply case	yes	13/01/2020	
Operational sensor head	yes	20/01/2020	
Sensor head envelope	no		10/04/2020
Sensor head transportation case	no		30/04/2020
Accessories and accessories case	no		30/04/2020

Table 6- Supplying of the AQQ's key elements.

We have received all the critical elements, required to operate and characterize the instrument in a laboratory environment. The measurement sequence of the AQQ-B, detailed in the section 1 of the deliverable D2.3 and in the Ref. 1, is composed of the atomic sample trapping, manipulation and detection, and requires a very fine adjustment of the laser beam durations, powers and frequencies during each of these steps. With the elements already at our disposal, we are able to perform this optimization of the sequence parameters and the characterization of the device in a controlled environment.

The sensor head envelope will be necessary for outdoor testing, because it allows to regulate the temperature of the instrument. Hence, it will be possible to carry out this activity once the sensor head envelope will be delivered (see Table 6).

Transport cases will be required for final shipment.

2.2 AQQ-B integration

Assembly of the different elements of the AQQ-B was completed at the beginning of January. Once the prototype of AQQ-B was assembled, we were able to trap atoms and to optimize the measurement sequence by the end of February. In mid-March, we performed the first gravity measurements in a laboratory environment, with the specified sensitivity.

Figure 3- Power supply and laser racks of the AQQ-B prototype in operation in the laboratory. The sensor head is also already functional, but not displayed on the picture for industrial property reasons.

2.3 User software

The user software (*AQG-GUI*) is the link between the final user and the AQG-B core program. It is user-friendly, and makes the operation of the AQG simple and intuitive. Very few actions are required from the final user. Below is a summary of the main steps of the program:

- invite the user to enter measurement parameters (tide models, setup height, ...)
- power on the different elements (air-conditioner, laser system, sensor-head electronics, ion pump driver)
- invite the user to set the tilt of the instrument with an intuitive interface
- switch on the laser and electronic components and subsystems in the right order. Verify that no error is detected at each step, before activating the next step
- start the measurement sequence, and make sure the number of trapped atoms is high enough
- automatically perform initial calibrations
- start the gravity measurement

The *AQG-GUI* software is currently installed and tested on the computer of the AQG-B prototype, which is continuously running in the laboratory at Muquans' facilities. Figure 2 shows the main software interface. The plot in the bottom shows measurements of g over an interval of about 15 hours.

Figure 4- User interface, with a g measurement over a night.

This interface is very close to its final version. Indeed, it was designed relying on the experience we gained from an already existing software, used to run the AQG-A. Updates are regularly applied to stay compliant with the evolutions and needs of the AQG-B.

3. Progress and current status

3.1 Work on the vibration rejection

As mentioned in the section 3.4 of deliverable D2.3, one of the major challenges in the realization of the prototype for the NEWTON-g project is the management of the vibration rejection in the particular environment of the summit zone of Mt. Etna. Indeed, this environment is completely different from the classic quiet sites for gravimetric measurement, where AQGs are usually operated.

Figure 3 shows acceleration PSDs recorded in different sites of interest. The signals recorded at PDN (summit zone of Etna, 2800m elevation; red curve) and SLN (southern slope of Etna, 1730m elevation; purple curve) sites on Mt Etna are broader and cover lower frequencies parts of the spectrum than signals we are used to work with.

Figure 5- Acceleration PSD obtained at Larzac, a classic low noise site for gravimetric measurement (green), at Talence, our urban test site, with (blue) and without (orange) absorbing pads under the AQG, at PDN (red) and SLN (purple) sites on Mt Etna.

The principle of the vibration rejection on the AQG, detailed in Ref. 1, is based on an active compensation of ground vibration in a closed loop system, which involves a high-performance classical accelerometer fixed on the top of the sensor head.

This vibration rejection system has not yet been tested in an environment with a strong low-frequency component of the seismic noise. Therefore, in order to estimate the performance of the AQG-B in these conditions, we performed numerical simulations based on the acceleration PSDs at the PDN and SLN sites (Figure 5).

The first column of the Table 7 shows the simulation results obtained by using the current classical accelerometer self-noise and transfer function. In these conditions, the simulations estimate that the AQG is not able to perform at all a measurement of g on any site of Mt Etna.

Site	Expected sensitivity of the measurement with the classical accelerometer	Expected sensitivity of the measurement with the seismometer
SLN	x	$70 \mu\text{Gal}/\sqrt{t} \rightarrow 1 \mu\text{Gal}$ in ~1h
MTN	x	$120 \mu\text{Gal}/\sqrt{t} \rightarrow 1 \mu\text{Gal}$ in ~4h
PDN	x	$120 - 250 \mu\text{Gal}/\sqrt{t} \rightarrow 1 \mu\text{Gal}$ in less than one day

Table 7- Result of simulation based on PSD recorded at SLN, MTN and PDN sites with the classical accelerometer currently used on our AQGs and with the seismometer that we consider using in the AQQ-B prototype. 'X' indicates that the noise is too high for the AQQ to operate in the given conditions.

Thanks to the anticipation of this problem, we were able to optimize our system by modifying the sensor. The chosen seismometer is more adapted to vibrations at low frequencies, and allows to obtain the simulated results shown in the second column of Table 7, which are encouraging. However, it is not possible to simulate experimentally this environment, so it is difficult to conclude on the behavior of the system for active compensation of vibrations, once the instrument is installed on the volcano.

We started to test the active compensation of vibrations with this new seismometer device on an AQQ-A in the urban environment of Muquans premises. The results, presented Table 8, are obtained with and without absorbing pads under the tripod of the sensor head (see PSDs on Figure 3).

	Sensitivity of the measurement with the classical accelerometer	Sensitivity of the measurement with the seismometer
With pads	$70 \mu\text{Gal}/\sqrt{t}$	$70 \mu\text{Gal}/\sqrt{t}$
Without pads	x	$120 \mu\text{Gal}/\sqrt{t}$

Table 8- Result of experiments realized on an AQQ-A in the Talence site with the classical accelerometer currently used on our AQGs and with the seismometer that we consider using in the AQQ-B prototype.

With the seismometer, we are able to perform a measurement of g in an urban environment, even without absorbing pads, which was not possible so far with our classical accelerometer. This result is also encouraging but we need further investigation to conclude. The next step will be to apply this new system on the AQQ-B and test it in different environments to confirm its robustness.

3.2 Gravity measurements in a laboratory environment

At the end of March 2020 (March 27 to 30) we collected the first time series of absolute gravity measurements from the AQQ-B, that meets the specification in term of sensitivity and long-term stability (Table 1) in a laboratory and urban environment (Muquans premises). Figure 3 shows the results of the measurement, with the plot of Allan deviation (left) and a 3-day time series (right).

Figure 6- Allan deviation of a g measurement obtained on a week-end (left), 10min-averaged g measurement with tides model (right).

The Allan deviation is an evaluation of the sensitivity and the stability of a sensor in the time domain with a representation of the statistical uncertainty evolution with the averaging time. The sensitivity obtained is 67 $\mu\text{Gal}/\sqrt{t}$ and the long-term stability is around 1 μGal . In other words, for an averaging time longer than 1 to 2 hours, the statistical uncertainty of the measurement is lower than 1 μGal .

Some optimization and characterization of the optical alignment in the sensor head, the laser frequencies during the sequence and the tracking parameters with the present mechanical accelerometer are needed before doing the final validation of the AQQ-B under laboratory conditions. An estimation of the bias on the absolute value of g is also required. These actions can be carried out remotely (see next section). Successively, we will need to perform further tests in out-of-the-lab conditions, before validating the AQQ-B for use under the conditions expected at the target installation site (summit zone of Mt. Etna).

4. Provisional schedule until the deployment

4.1 Planning towards the deployment, before the measures against the COVID-19

The following planning reflects the outcome of discussions during the “pre-deployment meeting” (INGV-OE, Catania, Italy 5-7 February 2020) and takes into account the current status of the instrument. It does not take into account the impact of the confinement measures applied by most European governments to fight the spread of the COVID-19. This issue is addressed in the sections 4.2 and 4.3. Indeed, at the time of this writing, the computer controlling the instrument can be accessed remotely, and most of the needed optimization operations can be carried out. However, if debug operations or adjustments are needed, that require the operator and technicians to be physically at the installation site, this could induce some delay because most Muquans employees are working from home (these operations are however in principle still possible in the current situations). Furthermore, some of our suppliers have strongly reduced their activity because of the COVID-19, and this can introduce some delay in the deliveries we are still waiting for (see section 2). Similarly, the day-to-day procurement of small components (electronics and optics) can be difficult because the building in which we are located no longer provides some services like handling the incoming deliveries. This requires us to adapt the needed actions on a case-by-case basis, depending on the possibilities of suppliers and shipment companies, which is leading to delays.

April:

Characterization of the device, estimation and correction of the bias affecting the g measurement.

May:

Test and validation to make the AQG-B fully compatible with operation under the conditions expected at the final installation site (Etna’s summit). This step includes the work on the vibration rejection (section 3.1), on the temperature management of the sensor head and on the power consumption limitation.

June:

Test under different environmental conditions and debug or optimization, if needed.

July:

Preparation of the delivery.

20th of July: shipment from Muquans to INGV-OE.

4.2 Risk analysis

Risk	Consequences	Mitigation strategy	Severity
Restricted access to Muquans premises and measures of social distance extended for a long period	Some tests and validations delayed, such as vibration rejection tests, temperature and power consumption management	Adaptation of the planning to optimize the time left after the confinement	Medium
Sensor head envelope not delivered on time because of the confinement	Tests on the management of the temperature in the sensor head delayed	Close discussions with supplier. Adaptation of general schedule to optimize workflow with available resources.	High
Transportation cases production and shipment delayed because of the confinement	Delivery to INGV delayed		Medium

Table 9- Status of risks

4.3 Possible evolutions linked to the impact of the COVID-19 pandemic

We describe three possible scenarios, depending on the amount of impact of the COVID-19 pandemic. In all three cases, we only take into account the impact of the epidemic on the activity of Muquans. If there is an impact on INGV-OE activities (for example the installation of the power supply system at the installation site is delayed), this can induce further delays.

First scenario: no delay

- The confinement measures are lifted at the end of April in France.
- All components delivered by May and no issue encountered during the scheduled actions (i.e. vibration rejection optimization, temperature and power consumption management).

Expected deployment schedule:

- The AQG-B is shipped to INGV on the 20th of July, as initially planned.
- Few days of measurement at INGV to check that everything is OK.
- Installation at PDN (Etna summit) at the beginning of August, and continuous measurement throughout August.
- In mid-September, depending on the quality of the acquired dataset, decision on whether the instrument will be left at PDN to keep measuring there, or moved to an alternative site, further away from the summit active craters.

Second scenario: moderate delay

- The confinement measures are lifted at the end of April in France.
- Not all components delivered during May and/or issue encountered during the scheduled actions (i.e. vibration rejection, temperature and power consumption management).

Expected deployment schedule:

- Shipment of the AQG to INGV-OE at the end of August.

- Few days of measurement at INGV to check that everything is OK.
- If possible, measurement test of few days at PDN in September.
- Decision on the final installation site (PDN or alternative site at lower elevation) before the end of September.

Third scenario:

- The confinement measurements last more than expected, with a significant impact on activities to be carried out on the prototype and delivery of needed parts.

Expected deployment schedule:

- Shipment of the AQQ to INGV significantly delayed without clear estimation of the duration (likely, after the summer).

Ref. 1: “Gravity measurement below $10^{-9}g$ with a transportable absolute quantum gravimeter, V. Ménot et al., Scientific reports, 17 august 2018”.